

STUDIES ON THE ELECTRIC POLARISATION AND STRUCTURE OF MOLECULAR COMPOUNDS. PART I

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Total polarisation of the molecular compounds of *sym.*-trinitrobenzene, 2:4-dinitrophenol, 2:4-dinitro-1-chlorobenzene with hydrocarbons, phenols and amines have been measured and the results discussed in relation to the structure of the molecular compounds.

Lowry (*Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 43, 218) has suggested that molecular compounds are formed by intermolecular co-ordination. Bennet and Wills (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 256) have supported the above view, pointing out that the deeper colour of the molecular compounds and the simple stoichiometric ratios in which the components are present are further evidence of the chemical linkage. The electronic formulation of these compounds is based on the suggestion that the nitro group with structure (I) is capable of acquiring structure (II) under certain conditions of activation.

The nitrogen of the nitro group in the activated state can accept a pair of electrons from amino group of amines and the compound is thus represented as

In case of molecular compounds of trinitrobenzene with hydrocarbons, one of the double bonds of hydrocarbons acts in the polarised form as

and donates a pair of electrons for the co-ordinate linkage.

Recently, evidence has been adduced against the formation of these compounds through a semipolar bond. Absorption spectra of compounds of *m*-dinitrobenzene and picric acid with a number of hydrocarbons (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1576) indicated that they were merely superimposition of curves of two components and neither the position of maxima nor $\log K$ indicated anything more than a small interaction. X-ray studies of *p*-iodoaniline-trinitrobenzene compound (Powell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 153) showed that intermolecular distances were greater than 3.5 Å which excludes the possibility of any chemical bonds between molecules. Briegleb and co-workers (*Z. Physik*, 1932, 19, 255 ; 1934, 26, 63) after extensive investigations on the heats of interaction, dissociation and combination concluded that the forces involved in molecular compound formation were those of interaction between a strongly polar group of one component and induced dipole in the other. The electrostatic forces thus involved are intermediate between Van der Waal's forces of attraction and true co-valencies.

In view of the above it was considered desirable to make a detailed study of the dielectric polarisation of the molecular compounds. We have therefore determined the total polarisation of the compounds of *sym.*-trinitrobenzene, 2:4-dinitro-1-chlorobenzene, 2:4-dinitrophenol and picric acid with hydrocarbons, phenols and amines with a view to discussing their structures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The molecular compounds of *sym.*-trinitrobenzene, 2:4-dinitrophenol and 2:4-dinitro-1-chlorobenzene were obtained by mixing the alcoholic solutions of the components in molecular proportions and boiling the mixture for a requisite time. The product was crystallised 3 or 4 times. Great care was taken to avoid any decomposition during crystallisation.

Total Polarisation Measurements

The dielectric constants of the solutions were determined on the heterodyne beat apparatus described before in a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 285). The working of the apparatus was checked by making determinations on a number of standard substances of known values of dielectric constants. The densities of solutions were determined by means of a specific gravity bottle. The refractive indices of the solutions were measured on the Pulfrich refractometer using sodium lamp as a standard source of light. Benzene with $\epsilon = 2.283$ at 20° was taken as the reference substance. The dielectric constants, molecular concentration, dipole moment and total polarisation of the components are given in Table I and those of the compounds with hydrocarbons in Table II, with amines in Table III, and with naphthols in Table IV.

TABLE I

No.	Name.	Mol. conc. (f ₁)	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Total polarisation P _T	Dipole moment (Debye unit).
1.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene	0.01071	293.2° A	2.513	329.6	3.743
2.	Picric acid	0.003869	293.0°	2.296	89.1	1.345
3.	2:4-Dinitrophenol	0.009549	293.0°	2.247	281.8	3.314
4.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene	0.008734	293.0°	2.442	296.6	3.275
5.	Naphthalene	0.01368	293.4°	2.287	45.3	0.0
6.	Benzidine	0.004788	293.5	2.291	85.63	1.375
7.	α -Methylnaphthalene	0.002604	292.8	2.296	48.4	0.2296
8.	α -Nitronaphthalene	0.005094	293.0	2.394	327.9	3.680
9.	Fluorene	0.010602	293.0°	2.286	54.7	0.28
10.	α -Naphthol	0.01217	292.8°	2.330	86.3	1.387
11.	β -Naphthol	0.01217	292.9°	2.331	88.77	1.412
12.	α -Naphthylamine	0.01227	292.6°	2.353	115.7	1.780
13.	β -Naphthylamine	0.01227	292.5°	2.362	130.0	1.904
14.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	0.006393	293.0°	2.460	430.80	4.231
15.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	0.004575	293.0°	2.450	520.7	4.680
16.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	0.01939	293.1°	2.376	95.48	1.773
17.	2:4:6-Trichloroaniline	0.00837	293.4°	2.351	154.10	2.168
18.	Phenanthrene	..	..	..	60.7	0.0*
19.	<i>sym.</i> -1:3:5-Trinitrobenzene	..	..	..	63.88	0.8*
20.	Bromonaphthalene	..	..	..	104	1.58*
21.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	..	..	..	201	2.80*
22.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	..	..	..	223	2.93
23.	<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline	..	..	..	104.4	1.77*
24.	<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline	..	..	..	187	2.65*
25.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	..	..	..	227.5	2.99*
26.	<i>p</i> -Iodoaniline	..	..	..	199.4	2.82*
27.	Aniline	..	..	..	79.7	1.55*

*The data for compounds 18 to 27 have been taken from the *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 80, Appendix.

TABLE II

Polynitro compounds with hydrocarbons.

No.	Name.	Mol. conc. (<i>f</i>)	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Total polarisation (P_T).	Dipole moment (Debye unit).
1.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene-naphthalene	0.002988	292.5°A	2.354	375.7	3.735
2.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene-benzidine	0.002514	292.5°	2.338	407.8	3.906
3.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene					
	—naphthalene	0.0025996	293.5°	2.289	76.93	0.8590
4.	Do —penanthrene	0.004526	293.0°	2.298	128.6	1.023
5.	Do —fluorene					
		0.006995	292.8°	2.299	111.5	0.8626
6.	Do —bromonaphthalene	0.004215	292.9°	2.308	144.7	1.741
7.	Do —benzidine	0.002327	292.7°	2.294	150.4	1.628
8.	Do — α -methylnaphthalene	0.002327	293.4°	2.298	126.4	1.227
9.	Do —1-nitronaphthalene	0.002277	293.0°	2.322	355.7	3.369
10.	Picric acid-naphthalene	0.002469	293.0°	2.921	121.5	1.148
11.	2:4-Dinitrophenol— α -naphthalene	0.005691	293.2°	2.367	279.7	3.022
12.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene— β -naphthalene	0.002674	293.2°	2.337	347.8	3.450

TABLE III

Polynitro compounds with amines.

No.	Name.	Mol. conc. (<i>f</i>)	Temp.	Dielectric constant.	Total polarisation.	Dipole moment (Debye unit).
1.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene					
	—naphthylamine	0.002846	292.8°A	2.359	442.8	3.956
2.	2:4-Dinitrophenol	0.002705	292.8	2.322	397.5	3.042
3.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene—	0.002559	292.9°	2.345	436.7	3.875
4.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—	0.002173	293.4°	2.292	128.8	1.811
	— β -naphthylamine	0.002483	293.0°	2.294	145.0	1.945
5.	Do — <i>m</i> -chloroaniline	0.002635	293.3°	2.311	212.5	2.597
7.	Do — <i>o</i> -chloroaniline	0.005191	293.2°	2.311	152.2	1.648
8.	Do — <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	0.002635	293.4°	2.312	216.3	2.631
9.	Do —2:4:6-trichloroaniline	0.004180	298.1	2.305	153.7	1.77
10.	Do — <i>o</i> -nitroaniline	0.002495	293.3°	2.362	546.4	4.466
11.	Do — <i>m</i> -nitroaniline	0.002527	293.0	2.391	556.3	4.58
12.	Do — <i>o</i> -bromoaniline	0.00457	292.7°	2.305	140.1	1.753
13.	Do — <i>m</i> -bromoaniline	0.002277	292.6°	2.306	228.3	2.649
14.	Do — <i>p</i> -bromoaniline	0.002277	292.5°	2.308	246.0	2.764
15.	Do — <i>p</i> -iodoaniline	0.002076	293.0°	2.305	216.7	2.563
16.	2:4-Dinitrophenol—aniline	0.003192	292.7°	2.328	261.2	3.016

TABLE IV

Polynitro compounds with naphthols.

No.	Name.	Mol. conc. (<i>f</i>)	Temp.	Dielectric constant	Total polarisation (P_T)	Dipole moment (Debye unit)
1.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitro-benzene— α -naphthol	0.004856	293.1°A	2.304	129.2	1.635
2.	Do— β -naphthol	0.002484	293.0°	2.293	124.8	1.512
3.	Picric acid— α -naphthol	0.002363	293.0°	2.299	173.5	1.937
4.	Do— β -naphthol	0.002363	293.0°	2.299	173.5	1.987
5.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene— α -naphthol	0.002548	292.5°	2.338	393.3	3.587
6.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene— β -naphthol	0.002548	292.5	2.340	404.2	3.688

DISCUSSION

The following tables record the values of the additive and experimental total polarisation and their differences.

TABLE V

Polynitro compounds with hydrocarbons

No.	Substance.	Total polarisation		
		Additive sum.	Exptl.	Difference.
1.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene—naphthalene	374.9	375.5	— 0.60
2.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene—benzidine	415.23	407.8	+ 7.43
3.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—naphthalene	109.18	76.93	+32.25
4.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—phenanthrene	124.58	128.2	— 3.62
5.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—fluorene	118.58	111.5	+ 7.08
6.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—benzidine	149.51	150.4	— 0.89
7.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—bromonaphthalene	167.88	144.7	+23.18
8.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—methylnaphthalene	112.28	126.4	—14.12
9.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene—nitronaphthalene	391.78	355.7	+36.08
10.	Picric acid—naphthalene	134.4	121.5	+12.9
11.	2:4-Dinitrophenol—naphthalene	327.1	279.7	+47.4
12.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene—naphthalene	341.0	347.8	— 5.9

TABLE VI

Polynitro compounds with naphthols.

No.	Substance.	Total polarisation		
		Additive sum	Exptl.	Difference.
1.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene— α -naphthol	150.18	129.2	+20.98
2.	Do — β -naphthol	152.65	124.8	+27.85
3.	Picric acid— α -naphthol	175.4	173.5	+ 1.9
4.	Do — β -naphthol	177.87	173.5	+ 4.37
5.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene— α -naphthol	382.9	393.2	—10.3
6.	Do — β -naphthol	385.37	404.2	—18.83

TABLE VII

Polynitro compounds with amines

No.	Substance.	Total polarisation		
		Additive sum.	Exptl.	Difference.
1.	<i>m</i> -Dinitrobenzene— α -naphthylamine	445.3	442.8	+ 2.5
2.	2:4-Dinitrophenol— β -naphthylamine	407.5	397.5	+10.0
3.	2:4-Dinitro-1-chlorobenzene— α -naphthylamine	412.3	438.7	—26.4
4.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene— β -naphthylamine	179.58	128.8	+50.78
5.	Do — α -naphthylamine	193.88	145.0	+48.88
6.	<i>sym</i> -Trinitrobenzene— <i>o</i> -chloroaniline	159.36	152.2	+ 7.16
7.	Do — <i>m</i> -chloroaniline	267.88	212.5	+55.38
8.	Do — <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	286.88	216.3	+70.58
9.	Do —trichloroaniline	217.98	153.7	+64.28
10.	Do — <i>o</i> -nitroaniline	494.68	546.4	—51.72
11.	Do — <i>m</i> -nitroaniline	584.58	556.2	+28.38
12.	Do — <i>o</i> -bromoaniline	168.28	140.1	+28.18
13.	Do — <i>m</i> -bromoaniline	250.88	228.3	+22.58
14.	Do — <i>p</i> -bromoaniline	291.33	246.0	+45.33
15.	Do — <i>p</i> -iodoaniline	263.28	216.7	+46.58
16.	2:4-dinitrophenol—aniline	361.80	261.20	+100.38

With the exception of about half a dozen cases, these differences are quite big. They are both positive and negative. The total polarisation,

$P = P_o + P_E + P_A + P_I + P_R$, where P_o , P_E , P_A , P_I , and P_R are orientation, electronic, atomic, ionic, and radical polarisations respectively

The change in any of the constituents forming P will result in a change in the value of P . Therefore, in order to ascertain the cause of the change in the total polarisation on the formation of molecular compounds, we have tried to study and discuss the change due to each of the constituents of the total polarisation.

Orientation polarisation P_o is due to the unsymmetry of the molecules. When the centres of the positive and negative charges are not coincident, the molecule possesses a dipole moment equal to the product of the charge and their distance of separation. In the case of polynitro substances, orientation polarisation is due to the nitro group attached to the benzene or other hydrocarbon nuclei, the hydrocarbons themselves being non-polar. In the molecular compounds with hydrocarbons these polynitro compounds combine with the ring as a whole and no special group combination takes place. No change therefore takes place in the orientation polarisation in the case of molecular compounds of polynitro substances with hydrocarbons.

P_E can be measured optically by means of refractive index (in the infra-red region), because the electromagnetic light waves can only cause the displacement of the electrons without affecting the atoms and the nuclei. Measurements of the electronic polarisation of the components and those of the molecular compounds show that there are no appreciable changes in the electronic polarisation on the formation of molecular compounds or in other words, electronic polarisation is not affected by the intermolecular changes accompanying the formation of the molecular compounds.

The remaining constituents forming the total polarisation are: $P_I + P_A + P_R$. The changes in the values of P_I are called interionic and those in the values of P_{AR} are called intermolecular changes of polarisation. In the case of heavier molecules the main contribution will be due to the ionic polarisation P_I^{AB} of the ions formed, and any intermolecular changes will be small compared with this term. Therefore, we may write as a first approximation for the differences of the vibrational polarisation term $P_{(IAR)}$ in the molecular compound formation.

$$P_{IAR} \equiv P_{IAR}^{AB} - (P_{IAR}^A + P_{IAR}^B) \approx P_I^{AB}$$

if we neglect the small differences in the intermolecular terms.

Now let us consider how the change in the total polarisation is due to the ionic polarisation. In the formation of the molecular compounds, there is a change in the structure of the electronic clouds of the constituents, because the two constituents while entering as uncharged molecules, are transformed into ions in the molecular compounds. The surrounding field will now have a profound effect on the electronic clouds of these highly polarisable molecules. If the surrounding field has a positive charge, it will compact or harden the electronic clouds. On the other hand, if the surrounding field has a negative charge it will soften the electronic clouds of the nucleus, in which it is present. The general effect of the electric

field upon polarisation has been studied by Smyth, Born and Heisenberg. They have shown that the effective polarisation (P_{eff}) in the presence of a strong field depends upon the polarisability (α) in the 'unstrained state' and the strength of the field. It is clear that α -effective is greater than α for positive charges and α -effective is less than α for negative charges.

Although it is possible to explain to a small extent both negative and positive differences of the polarisation of the molecular compounds from the sum of the components by the causes explained above, yet there are in most cases differences of a very high order. This indicates that there is some other phenomenon along with the above factors which is at work for such big polarisation differences. It therefore appears that in the formation of these molecular compounds, different resonance forms of the components take part in the compound formation. The extent to which a resonance form reacts depends upon the energy condition as well as the second reacting component.

For the quantitative treatment of the resonance structures and the effect of the rotational polarisation on the formation of molecular compounds, it was considered necessary to compare the dipole moments also of the above compounds with those of the additive sum of the components. These results will be described in the next communication.

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